

Classifying and mining design diagrams in source code repositories using transfer learning

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports on the implementation of a design diagram classifier using transfer learning and fine-tuning. For the study, we built a labeled data set with 5981 images identifying the following design diagram categories: none (no design diagram represented), activity diagram, sequence diagram, class diagram, component diagram, use case diagram, and cloud diagrams. We then used the dataset, transfer learning, and fine-tuning techniques to train a specialized DenseNet169 convolutional network, starting from a model pre-trained on ImageNet. The newly trained network achieved a prediction accuracy of 98.6% (0.986 ± 0.0017) and an F1-score of 98.3% (0.983 ± 0.0025). Repository mining techniques were then used to analyze 2,469,206 images, equivalent to 231 GB of data, obtained from 287,201 repositories. The analysis revealed that design diagrams are often outdated relative to the project's evolution; on average, diagrams were last updated 554 days prior to the repository's latest commit. This significant lag suggests that while diagrams are present, practitioners primarily rely on the source code as the living design artifact.

1. Introduction

Developing complex software artifacts through collaborations among geographically distributed teams has become common in the software industry. Developers and teams have adopted automated tools to support configuration management, testing, continuous delivery, and continuous integration, among other practices. Tools such as *GitHub*, *GitLab*, and *Bitbucket* are now used by teams of developers collaborating globally on software projects. The adoption of these platforms by the software community resulted in the automation of the development life cycle, the standardization of software repositories, and the generation of massive amounts of metrics and meta-data. This has opened new opportunities for empirical research in software engineering, where *repository mining* is becoming a prominent technique for analyzing and understanding software development patterns and trends.

One significant problem that can now be explored in more depth through *repository mining* techniques is understanding *how practitioners document software design*. Since the recognition of the "Software Crisis" [1] in 1968, the questions of what software design is and what techniques are better to achieve "good" software design have been central points of discussion in the software community. The debate has been intense, and several responses have been given. Starting

with Dijkstra's *intellectually manageable programs* with formal proofs of correctness [2], passing by calculational logic [3,4], formal specification languages [5], formal verification systems [5], graphical modeling techniques with semiformal modeling languages [6], and current more pragmatic approaches using the source code as the primary design artifact [7]. We are still far from understanding the process of how people create knowledge, but thanks to the unprecedented volume of design artifacts available in modern code repositories, researchers can now empirically examine hypotheses on software design practices and explore further how practitioners create knowledge in software projects. However, there are still significant challenges when examining hypotheses about software design artifacts, such as analyzing design diagrams stored in repositories as image files. On the one hand, extracting information from binary images is inherently difficult and becomes an AI problem in its own right. Conversely, training models to classify or extract information from these images would require large training datasets and substantial computational power. For scenarios like this, *transfer learning* is a promising approach, leveraging pre-trained models to adapt to new domains with limited data.

Given the above, the goal of this paper is twofold: (1) explore fundamental questions around software design and documentation practices,

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and (2) evaluate to what extent *transfer learning* could support the development of tools for *repository mining*. In this research, we are interested in studying how design knowledge is recorded and managed within software projects. We understand that analyzing the flow of knowledge in any human activity is a complex and challenging task because we are still far from understanding how human knowledge is created. However, using repository mining with machine learning tools enables experimental testing of complex knowledge-related conjectures that may help understand the nature of knowledge and improve the practice of software design. Instead of analyzing each design artifact to understand how engineers acquired this knowledge and how effective a particular artifact was at storing and transmitting it, we adopt a more restrictive approach. This research proposes analyzing design diagrams as a representative design artifact to study how design knowledge is managed within software projects. In particular, we want to understand what type of diagrams engineers use and how effective they are for documenting the actual design. We chose design diagrams because they are widely accepted for design documentation, software engineers are commonly trained in using them, and we can compare them with the actual design represented in the source code. Concretely, this study presents the following contributions:

- A workflow for analyzing images in software engineering repositories using a convolutional neural network (CNN) pre-trained on ImageNet. The model was further adapted to the specific task of diagram classification via *transfer learning* and *fine-tuning*.
- A labeled dataset comprising 5981 images, categorized into *none*, activity diagram, sequence diagram, class diagram, component diagram, use case diagram, and cloud diagram. This dataset serves as a valuable resource for the research community.
- An experimental evaluation of the classifier applied to 2,469,206 images extracted from 287,201 repositories. During the experiment, we investigated the presence and usage of design diagrams in software repositories. We also discuss possible implications of the experimental results and links to new software design theories.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the motivation and the research questions. Section 3 provides an overview of concepts on repository mining, convolutional neural networks, and transfer learning. Section 4 discusses the state of the art in machine learning for image classification and image mining of code repositories. In Section 5, we detail the comprehensive methodology and implementation, covering dataset construction, the machine learning model architecture and training, and the repository mining pipeline. Section 6 presents the experimental results and addresses the research questions raised. Section 7 explores the theoretical implications of the findings and discusses conjectures about software design practices. Section 8 addresses potential threats to validity. Finally, Section 9 concludes the paper and discusses future work.

2. Motivation and research questions

We want to apply quantitative experimental methods to address complex and interesting knowledge management questions during software development projects. Even though we know that understanding how software engineers generate knowledge is complex, and our theories of how humans create knowledge are incipient and incomplete, recent developments in machine learning and the constant evolution of computer hardware have opened the door to experimental testing of complex knowledge-related conjectures using vast amounts of data.

In this paper, we propose analyzing the use of design diagrams in software repositories to understand which types of diagrams engineers use and to what extent they are used throughout the project's evolution to store the actual design. For the analysis, we implement repository mining tools supported by *transfer learning* and *fine-tuning*. This approach will allow us to demonstrate the capabilities and possibilities of

machine learning technologies in repository mining, understand how software practitioners use design diagrams and conjecture hypotheses related to the practice, philosophy, and art of software design.

In particular, the research questions addressed in this work are described as follows:

- RQ1:** What is the impact of *transfer learning* and *fine-tuning* techniques on the performance of a software design diagram classifier?
- RQ2:** How common is it to upload images to *GitHub* repositories, and if they are diagrams, what kind of diagrams are they?
- RQ3:** What is the proportion of *Git* projects that contain diagrams, and how are they distributed by diagram type?
- RQ4:** How do the timestamps of the last diagram update compare with the repository's latest commit, and what does this indicate about the relevance and utility of these diagrams?

3. An overview on repository mining and transfer learning

This section elaborates on the core concepts of this research, namely *repository mining* and machine learning techniques for diagram-on-image analysis, focusing on convolutional neural networks as the model architecture and transfer learning as the technique applied to enhance the performance of the convolutional neural network.

3.1. Software repository mining

Software repository mining [8] is a field of software engineering that analyzes the data available in software repositories, such as source code versions, comments, issues, and pull requests, among others, to extract useful information. This information can be used to understand and improve the development process and to assist developers. For example, by predicting issues based on past errors, recognizing present patterns when an error occurs, or, as in this document, by extracting design information from design diagrams in repositories to perform analyses and identify undesirable patterns or opportunities for improvement.

Software repository mining involves tools and techniques such as models for storing and retrieving software metrics. In addition, it can encompass advanced aspects such as data analysis and be complemented with other techniques such as machine learning [9].

3.2. Convolutional neural networks

A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a deep learning architecture [10] commonly used for image and video processing tasks, such as image classification and segmentation. This kind of network leverages the spatial structure of the image under the premise that the value of a pixel is linked to its adjacent ones, which make up structures, shapes, and patterns that facilitate understanding the image's content [11]. The CNN learns and assigns numerical values or weights to aspects of an image to distinguish them. They are characterized by (1) requiring less preprocessing than other classification algorithms and (2) being able to identify characteristics automatically,² i.e., without a prior feature-engineering process and manual selection of characteristics [12].

The convolutional network comprises multiple layers where the convolution operation is performed. This operation seeks to reduce the training images to a more manageable form by focusing on critical features for a good prediction. First, a filter based on a group of adjacent pixels is applied, learning the appropriate values for each filter during the training process, also known as the *kernel*. Then, the filter generates a new image representation called a feature map, where the

² Through the learned edge detection filters.

bright areas are the activated regions that pass the filter, indicating that the feature the filter was designed to identify has been detected.

The feature map is a critical concept in CNNs as it progressively abstracts the image content into higher-level representations. Fig. A.1 (see Appendix) illustrates how the network transforms a raw image into feature maps at different levels of abstraction, starting from edge detection in the early layers to more complex patterns in deeper layers.

Each layer in the convolutional network has multiple filters that use all outputs of the previous layer as input. More complex filters are created by composing the basic ones. Patterns detected by filters in the first layers, such as edges or straight line segments, can combine into circles and other more complex structures, which, in turn, compose medium-level concepts such as an eye, an ear, etc. These, in turn, compose high-level concepts such as a face, a car, or a landscape, known as patterns of spatial hierarchies [13], as depicted in Fig. A.2 (see Appendix).

3.3. Transfer learning

Transfer learning is a technique for transferring knowledge learned by one neural network to another when the latter aims to solve a similar task. The idea is to leverage a pre-trained model, typically trained on a large, diverse dataset, to solve a new problem with limited data. The assumption is that certain features learned in the first task can be useful for the second task.

Transfer learning involves freezing some layers of a pre-trained network to preserve the learned parameters. New layers can be added to adapt the model to a new problem while keeping the frozen layers intact. The unfrozen part of the network is then trained on the new data. An additional step is *fine-tuning*, a technique that involves unfreezing either the entire model or part of it and retraining it with a low learning rate. Fine-tuning is most effective after the classifier on top has been trained. If the classifier is not trained first, the error signal during backpropagation may overwhelm and destabilize the previously learned representations, especially in the network's lower, more general layers. This method can be visualized by dividing the network into four main sections, as depicted in Fig. A.3 (see Appendix): the input, the initial layers (responsible for learning general features that are easier to transfer), the final layers (responsible for learning task-specific features), and the top layer, where the final classification is performed [11].

The steps for performing transfer learning with fine-tuning are as follows:

1. Take a pre-trained base network and add a custom classification head on top.
2. Freeze the majority or all of the layers in the pre-trained base network to prevent their parameters from being updated during the initial training phase.
3. Train the custom classification head on top of the frozen base network.
4. Unfreeze some or all of the layers in the base network.
5. Continue training the unfrozen layers and the custom classification head with a lower learning rate to fine-tune the model.

The main benefit of transfer learning is the reduction of the computations and the amount of data required for training. Since the network has already learned many basic patterns for edge and simple-shape identification in the initial layers, it only needs to learn specific compound patterns for the new problem. An example of character recognition illustrates the technique: the characteristics learned in the initial layers of a model for alphabet letter classification can be beneficial for a model for digit classification. As the patterns required to identify a letter or a digit are similar, they share low-level patterns, such as line segments and edges, and mid-level patterns, such as circles and lines, that make up a letter or a digit [14].

4. State of the art

This section reviews related work on *repository mining of diagram images* and the methods for identifying and classifying these images, focusing on advancements in machine learning techniques.

4.1. Repository mining applied to diagram images

An ad-hoc literature review reveals that few studies have focused on analyzing diagram images in the context of repository mining. For instance, in [15], the authors created a UML diagram dataset using repository mining techniques. They extracted multiple repositories from GitHub using GHTorrent and the GitHub API. The repository content was then searched for files that could potentially be diagrams. A filtering process was performed based on file extensions (jpg, jpeg, png, bmp, svg, gif) and file names (e.g., diagram, architecture, design, UML). Further filtering was based on parameters such as image size, and duplicates were removed. Finally, they used a UML diagram classifier, proposed in [16], which employed logistic regression and feature extraction methods.

Other studies [17,18] have also explored tools for identifying whether a project contains diagrams and how those diagrams evolve over time. These studies similarly utilized tools like GHTorrent and the GitHub API for metadata extraction, followed by a pre-filtering process based on file names and extensions, and employed machine learning techniques like random forests for classification.

4.2. Diagram image classification

Our literature review suggests that (1) most studies focus on UML diagrams, neglecting other types of artifacts such as cloud architecture diagrams, and (2) most related studies rely on classical (supervised) machine learning methods.

Several studies have attempted to identify and classify diagrams from images, primarily focusing on UML diagrams to determine the type of UML diagram represented in an image. A notable example is [19], where instead of directly using machine learning for classification, a tool (Img2UML [20]) was employed to extract text from images, followed by a set of fixed criteria for classification.

Other works [16,18,21] have focused on feature extraction strategies to enhance the effectiveness of diagram classifiers, employing classical machine learning algorithms such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), logistic regression, and random forests.

Regarding detecting non-UML diagrams, the available literature is relatively scarce, with only a few studies applying machine learning. Most studies rely on alternative methods adapted for specific domains. For example, in [22], the authors propose a framework called IMEAV for processing architectural diagrams and extracting relevant information. Similarly, [23] analyzed Finite State Automata diagrams using image processing and pattern recognition techniques, bypassing machine learning in favor of generating Constraint Multiset Grammar (CMGs) models based on visual patterns.

Recent advances in hardware and software have enabled Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to become the state of the art in image classification tasks [24]. One of the pioneering works that applied CNNs and transfer learning to diagram classification was [25], demonstrating the benefits of using a pre-trained network on the *ImageNet* dataset and transferring that general knowledge to the domain of diagram detection.

Subsequent studies, such as [26], aimed to classify three specific types of UML diagrams along with non-UML images. A dataset of 3231 images across four categories was constructed, and various architectures (*MobileNet*, *DenseNet*, *NasNet*, *ResNet*, *Inception*, and a custom model) were tested. *DenseNet169* and the custom architecture yielded the best results. While transfer learning was employed, the implementation lacked details on whether fine-tuning was performed, leaving this

Fig. 1. The proposed end-to-end pipeline for diagram classification and mining. The process spans from the initial curation of a labeled dataset to the large-scale extraction and analysis of 2.4 million images from GHTorrent.

aspect unclear. Moreover, the comparison did not include architectures like *Xception*, *NASNetLarge*, and *EfficientNet*, which have shown superior performance in certain tasks. Another relevant study [27] used a dataset of 3298 images for binary classification to determine if an image was a UML diagram. On the other hand, our research includes repository mining and fine-tuning, broadens the classification scope to include additional diagram types, such as cloud diagrams, and applies these techniques to address software engineering challenges.

In [28], a deep network combined with a low-shot learning strategy was proposed to reduce the number of learning parameters when classifying UML class and sequence diagrams. However, the study was limited to only two types of diagrams, and transfer learning was not applied.

Further, other studies focused on creating UML diagram image datasets. For example, [17] provided a list of repositories containing UML images, while [29] created an online repository of UML diagrams in XMI format. In contrast, [15] combined manual work with detection algorithms to identify 93,596 UML diagrams from 24,717 repositories, with 61.8% of the detected diagrams in image format. This demonstrates a significant presence of diagram images in repositories. Our approach, however, leverages transfer learning, fine-tuning, and repository mining, applying these techniques specifically within the context of Software Engineering.

Given these insights, we identified an opportunity to further explore repository mining, particularly focusing on the diagram images within repositories. Our approach uses CNNs with transfer learning and fine-tuning, expanding the classification to include additional types of diagrams beyond UML.

5. Methodology and implementation

In this section, we detail the methodology and implementation process employed throughout our investigation. The workflow is structured in four key phases: dataset construction, model architecture design, iterative training and refinement, and large-scale repository mining. This comprehensive framework enables the classification and analysis of various software design artifacts from source code repositories. Fig. 1 provides an overview of this workflow.

5.1. Dataset construction and labeling

The foundation of our approach is a labeled image dataset containing 5981 images classified into seven categories: none, activity diagram, sequence diagram, class diagram, component diagram, use case diagram, and cloud diagram.³

³ Cloud diagrams refer to visual representations that depict cloud-based services, infrastructure, and relationships within a cloud environment. While not part of standard UML notation, these diagrams are increasingly used in modern software architectures to represent cloud services (e.g., AWS, Azure). Given the growing importance of cloud computing, their inclusion allows us to examine the usage of service architectures in software repositories.

Fig. 2. Dataset construction process: extraction, pre-processing, and labeling tasks.

5.1.1. Data sources and collection

The dataset was compiled using a hybrid approach of automated scraping and manual selection. Images were sourced from:

1. **Google Image Search:** A custom Python script utilizing Selenium collected images based on specific diagram keywords.
2. **Lindholmen Dataset:** We incorporated UML models from the existing Lindholmen dataset [15].
3. **Git Repositories:** Additional assets and miscellaneous images (primarily for the 'None' category) were extracted directly from software repositories.

Fig. 2 illustrates the extraction, pre-processing, and labeling pipeline.

5.1.2. Normalization and filtering

All collected images were converted to *JPG* in *RGB* format and rescaled to 224×224 pixels. We utilized the *Lanczos* resampling algorithm [30] for rescaling. This algorithm was selected for its ability to preserve fine details, such as the thin lines connecting components in diagrams, which often disappear with standard rescaling methods [31].

Following normalization, a SHA-1 hash was computed from the standardized binary content of each image to detect and remove exact duplicates. While automated perceptual hashing was not employed, the dataset's manageable size allowed for a subsequent manual quality control process. In this phase, annotators visually reviewed the images to identify and discard not only low-resolution or corrupted files, but also near-duplicates that might have bypassed the cryptographic hash check.

5.1.3. Labeling process

To ensure high-quality labeling, the labeling process was supported by a custom semi-automated script implemented in Python using the OpenCV library. The script displayed each image in a pop-up window, allowing the annotator to assign a label by pressing a designated key. This streamlined process was essential for maintaining consistency across thousands of images.

Two independent annotators classified the images into the seven predefined categories. The results were stored in separate CSV files. Subsequently, we automatically identified entries where the assigned labels differed. These discrepancies were resolved through a joint validation session, where both labelers reviewed the conflicting images to

Fig. 3. Transfer learning model architecture. The tensor output shape before flattening is (None, 7, 7, 1664). The “Frozen early layers” comprise Dense Blocks 1 through 3, while “Re-trainable last layers” include Dense Block 4 and the Classification Head.

Table 1

Number of images per category for the pre-processed dataset.

Label	Category	Quantity
0	None	1451
1	Activity Diagram	591
2	Sequence Diagram	800
3	Class Diagram	972
4	Component Diagram	360
5	Use Case Diagram	844
6	Cloud Diagram	963
-	Total	5981

reach a final consensus. Table 1 summarizes the final distribution of the 5981 images.

5.2. Model architecture and transfer learning

We employed transfer learning to train a convolutional neural network (CNN) for diagram classification. We selected the *DenseNet169* [32] architecture, pre-trained on ImageNet, as our base model. DenseNet169 was chosen for its superior feature reuse capability and ability to mitigate the vanishing gradient problem [33]. Preliminary experiments indicated it outperformed ResNet and VGG architectures for this specific task [26].

5.2.1. Architecture customization

As illustrated in Fig. 3, we adapted the model by removing the original classification head and adding custom layers. The input images were resized to 224×224 pixels to match the pre-trained requirements. The modified network includes:

- A flatten layer that contains the global feature aggregation combining pre-learned features.
- A Batch Normalization layer.
- A single extra dense layer with 128 units.
- A Dropout layer (0.5) for regularization.
- A second Batch Normalization layer.
- A final Softmax layer for the seven-class prediction.

Fig. 4. Impact on model's validation accuracy and loss function by increasing dense extra layers (0, 1, 2) in the pre-trained network. The mean (validation accuracy \pm standard deviation) at the last epoch was 0.947 ± 0.007 , 0.962 ± 0.010 and 0.969 ± 0.002 for 0, 1 and 2 extra layers, respectively, with corresponding validation losses of 1.38 ± 0.12 , 0.14 ± 0.05 and 0.11 ± 0.01 .

5.2.2. Hyperparameter and architecture optimization

To determine the optimal network configuration, we conducted a series of incremental, dependency-aware experiments, each designed to refine a specific architectural component while keeping all other settings fixed. This sequential approach ensures that the effect of each modification is isolated, and that subsequent experiments build directly upon the best-performing configuration identified in the previous step.

Number of Extra Layers. First, we evaluated the depth of the custom classification head. We added a layer to the pre-trained network to combine pre-learned image features, followed by additional dense layers. As shown in Fig. 4, adding a single dense layer improved performance, but increasing the depth beyond that (adding 2 or more layers) slightly reduced the number of outputs of the original model and did not significantly impact performance. Consequently, we proceeded with a single additional dense layer. The single-layer configuration identified here served as the baseline for all subsequent experiments.

Layer Size Next, using the optimal one-layer configuration from the previous step, we sought the appropriate size for this dense layer. A layer of 512 units increases the parameters by 41 million, whereas a layer of 64 units adds only 5 million parameters. A larger network implies greater learning capacity but also increases the risk of overfitting—memorizing images rather than learning general patterns. Fig. 5 shows that the larger size (512) resulted in worse performance due to overfitting. A size of 128 units provided the best balance between classification performance and computational overhead.

Dropout With the architecture (one dense layer with 128 units) fixed from earlier tests, we next evaluated the impact of adding a

Fig. 5. Impact of increasing units in a dense initial layer in the pre-trained network. The mean (\pm standard deviation) validation accuracy at the last epoch for 64, 128, 256 and 512 units was 0.968 ± 0.005 , 0.966 ± 0.005 , 0.971 ± 0.005 and 0.963 ± 0.006 , respectively, with corresponding validation losses of 0.11 ± 0.01 , 0.11 ± 0.01 , 0.12 ± 0.02 and 0.15 ± 0.04 .

Fig. 6. Impact of adding the dropout layer in the pre-trained network. The mean (\pm standard deviation) validation accuracy with and without dropout was 0.967 ± 0.006 and 0.964 ± 0.006 , respectively, with corresponding validation losses of 0.12 ± 0.03 and 0.15 ± 0.04 .

Fig. 7. Impact of retraining the last dense block in the pre-trained network. The mean (\pm standard deviation) validation accuracy for models with retrained versus frozen last dense block was 0.964 ± 0.001 and 0.953 ± 0.006 , respectively, with corresponding validation losses of 0.12 ± 0.01 and 0.14 ± 0.02 .

dropout layer to further prevent overfitting. Dropout randomly sets the activation values of a subset of units to zero during training, reducing co-adaptation and improving generalization. As shown in Fig. 6, incorporating dropout improved the model’s validation accuracy while also reducing the loss values.

Impact of Retraining and Fine-Tuning. Finally, building upon the optimized classification head (single layer, 128 units, with dropout), we experimentally validated the extent to which the base network should be unfrozen. We compared utilizing fixed ImageNet features versus retraining the final blocks. As shown in Fig. 7, retraining the last dense block (while keeping earlier layers frozen) allowed the model to learn features more relevant to diagram classification. Furthermore, we tested a full fine-tuning strategy (unfreezing all layers with a low learning rate). As illustrated in Fig. 8, this process yielded the highest accuracy. Based on these experimental results, we adopted the two-phase training protocol detailed in the following section.

5.2.3. Experimental setup

The model training and experiments were conducted on an Apple MacBook Pro (16-inch) equipped with an M1 Pro chip and 16 GB of RAM. The implementation utilized Python 3.9 and TensorFlow/Keras

Fig. 8. Impact of the fine-tuning process on the pre-trained network. The transfer learning baseline achieved a validation accuracy of 0.9674 ± 0.0017 and a validation loss of 0.111 ± 0.008 . Fine-tuning improved performance to 0.9871 ± 0.0029 validation accuracy and 0.0345 ± 0.0003 validation loss.

2.9.1. Despite the limited memory compared to large-scale cluster environments, the efficiency of Transfer Learning allowed us to fine-tune the DenseNet169 model effectively within these hardware constraints.

5.3. Iterative training and refinement strategy

To ensure the robustness of the classifier before large-scale mining, we implemented the training strategy derived from the optimization results in Section 5.2.2.

5.3.1. Training protocol

The final training process consisted of two distinct phases to maximize the benefits of transfer learning:

Phase 1: Transfer Learning with Partial Freezing. Initially, we trained the model using an Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 1×10^{-3} for 10 epochs. During this phase, we applied the strategy validated in Fig. 7: the initial layers of the DenseNet base were frozen to retain generic ImageNet features, while the final convolutional block Dense Block 4 (conv5) and the custom classification head were left unfrozen. This allowed the model to adapt to high-level diagram features without destroying the pre-learned feature extractors.

Phase 2: Full Fine-Tuning. Subsequently, we unfroze the **entire network** and performed fine-tuning with a significantly reduced learning rate of 1×10^{-6} . This phase implements the findings from Fig. 8, allowing for subtle adjustments to the entire feature extraction hierarchy to better suit the specific domain of software diagrams.

To evaluate performance, we employed *repeated random sub-sampling validation* (Monte Carlo cross-validation). The dataset was randomly partitioned into training (80%) and validation (20%) subsets. We repeated this process four times using distinct random seeds. The reported performance metrics are the mean values across these iterations, ensuring the results are not artifacts of a specific data split.

5.3.2. Dataset refinement and retraining

To validate the model’s readiness for unseen repository data, we ran a preliminary classification on a subset of Git repositories. We identified images where the model yielded low-confidence predictions (confidence $< 30\%$). Visual inspection revealed that these were primarily specific non-diagram artifacts (e.g., circuit diagrams, construction plans, GUI screenshots) that were underrepresented in the ‘None’ category.

To address this, we manually labeled and added 800 of these low-confidence images to the training dataset, bringing the total to 5981. We then retrained the network from scratch using the two-phase approach described above. This refinement yielded significant improvements:

- The average prediction confidence increased from 98.1% to 99.3%.
- The accuracy specifically for diagram categories increased from 80.4% to 83.4%.
- The number of false positives (images incorrectly detected as diagrams) was reduced by nearly 8000.

5.4. Repository mining pipeline

With the optimized and retrained model, we proceeded to the large-scale mining phase. We utilized the GHTorrent dataset [34] to identify potential repositories.

5.4.1. Data extraction

From an initial list of 510,068 repositories in GHTorrent, we successfully cloned 287,201 repositories. From these, we extracted 2,469,206 image files, totaling 231 GB of data. The extraction was filtered to include only standard image formats (*jpg*, *png*, *jpeg*) with a resolution greater than 100×100 pixels.

The mining process was strictly limited to public repositories on GitHub. The data extraction and analysis were conducted in compliance with GitHub's Terms of Service regarding public information. Furthermore, the replication package (code and dataset) [35–38] is made available under the Apache 2.0 License to ensure open reproducibility.

5.4.2. Metadata and freshness analysis

For every image, we extracted metadata including the repository name and the timestamp of the last modification. Crucially, we determined image ‘freshness’ using the Git commit timestamp of the specific image file rather than the file system timestamp. This ensures the date reflects the actual moment the developer updated the design artifact, allowing for an accurate analysis of how diagrams evolve relative to the source code.

5.4.3. Classification

The images were processed in batches of 1000. Each image was normalized and passed through the trained DenseNet169 model. The classifier outputs a probability distribution across the seven categories; the category with the highest probability was assigned as the predicted label. All results were stored in a CSV file [36] for the analysis presented in the following section.

6. Study results

This section addresses the research questions introduced in Section 1. The answers are based on the experimental evaluation of the proposed classification model and on the outcomes of its application on a selection of Git repositories.

6.1. RQ1 - what is the impact of transfer learning and fine-tuning techniques on the performance of the classifier?

We employed several performance metrics to evaluate the effectiveness of transfer learning and fine-tuning techniques in our image classifier:

- **Accuracy:** The proportion of correctly predicted samples out of all samples.
- **Precision or positive-predicted value:** The ratio of correctly identified images in a category to all images identified as that category.
- **Recall or sensitivity:** The fraction of true positives identified from a category.
- **F1-score:** The harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a balance between the two.

These metrics are derived from the following classification outcomes:

- **True Positives (TP):** Images correctly classified into their respective categories.
- **False Positives (FP):** Images incorrectly classified into a category they do not belong to.

Table 2

Performance metrics of the classifier using transfer learning with fine-tuning, evaluated on an 80/20 train-validation random split.

Category	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
None	0.9700	0.9864	0.9782	295
Activity Diagram	0.9828	0.9661	0.9744	118
Sequence Diagram	0.9866	0.9932	0.9899	148
Class Diagram	0.9911	0.9911	0.9911	225
Component Diagram	0.9839	0.9531	0.9683	64
Use Case Diagram	0.9941	0.9941	0.9941	169
Cloud Diagram	0.9943	0.9831	0.9887	178
Accuracy			0.9850	1197
Macro avg	0.9861	0.9810	0.9835	1197
Weighted avg	0.9850	0.9850	0.9850	1197

Fig. 9. Accuracy and loss function plots for the model using transfer learning with fine-tuning, transfer learning only, and training the entire network from scratch.

- **True Negatives (TN):** Images correctly identified as not belonging to a specific category.
- **False Negatives (FN):** Images of a category that were incorrectly classified as belonging to another category.

The performance metrics were calculated using the standard formulas:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

$$F1\text{-score} = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

To answer this question, we evaluated the DenseNet169 model configuration described in Section 5. The evaluation utilized the Monte Carlo cross-validation strategy (4 iterations) to ensure the reported metrics reflect the model's stability and robustness, rather than artifacts of a specific data split.

6.1.1. Performance evaluation

Table 2 provides detailed performance metrics of the classifier using the transfer learning and fine-tuning methodology described in Section 5. As shown in Fig. 9, transfer learning noticeably improves the classifier's performance: the learning curve is less steep, and the final accuracy is substantially higher than when training the network from scratch. Fine-tuning further enhances the model, resulting in high accuracy and strong generalization.

The final model achieved an accuracy of 98.6% (0.986 ± 0.0017) and an F1-score of 98.3% (0.983 ± 0.0025) on the testing set, underscoring the effectiveness of our fine-tuning and transfer learning approach. These results were consistently observed across four iterations of Monte Carlo cross-validation, indicating the model's robustness and reliability in classifying design diagrams from diverse software projects.

To provide a more granular analysis of misclassifications, we generated a Confusion Matrix (Table 3). To ensure methodological rigor,

Table 3

Confusion Matrix for the classification of design diagrams (Validation Set, $N = 1197$).

True\Predicted	None	Act.	Seq.	Class	Comp.	Use	Cloud
None	280	0	1	0	0	0	0
Activity	0	134	0	0	0	0	0
Sequence	0	0	155	0	1	0	0
Class	0	0	0	189	1	0	0
Component	1	0	1	0	69	0	2
Use Case	1	0	0	0	0	164	0
Cloud	1	0	0	0	0	0	197

this matrix was computed using a fixed random seed ($seed = 42$) for the train-validation split, guaranteeing that the evaluated images were completely unseen by the model during the training phase. The results demonstrate high discriminatory power across all categories. The ‘Component Diagram’ category exhibited the highest relative error rate, with minor confusion against ‘Cloud’ and ‘Sequence’ diagrams. This is likely due to the visual similarity between block-based component structures and certain cloud architecture representations. However, these errors remain negligible compared to the overall correct predictions.

Comparison with Training from Scratch

Training the network from scratch with the same dataset would likely result in overfitting due to the limited size of 5981 images. The transfer learning approach mitigates overfitting and achieves higher accuracy and better generalization, highlighting the necessity of leveraging pre-trained models and larger datasets for effective image classification.

Repository Mining Results

Regarding RQ2, RQ3, and RQ4, the statistics obtained through the repository mining process lead to several observations that answer them as follows.

6.2. RQ2 - How common is it to upload images to GitHub repositories, and if they are diagrams, what kind of diagrams are they?

Out of the analyzed repositories, 98,207 (approximately 34%) contained at least one image. However, most of these images fall under the ‘None’ category, comprising 97% of all images. Among the diagrams class diagrams are the most prevalent, while sequence diagrams and cloud diagrams are the least common. Specifically, cloud diagrams are only present in 1.7% of repositories and account for just 0.17% of all images. This distribution suggests that cloud diagrams are rarely used in repositories.

To compute the average prediction confidence for each image category, we analyzed the probability scores generated during the prediction phase and stored in the results CSV file. For every image, the classifier outputs a probability distribution, we extracted the probability value corresponding to the predicted class. The average confidence for a category is calculated as the mean of these probabilities for all images assigned to that category:

$$\text{AveragePredictionConfidence} = \frac{\sum \text{ProbabilityOfPredictedClass}}{\text{TotalImagesInCategory}}$$

Table 4 presents these confidence scores. Additionally, during the analysis of the results, we utilized a confidence threshold (0.3) to identify and filter out low-confidence predictions, which were essentially ‘noise’ or non-diagram images.

6.3. RQ3 - What is the proportion of git projects that contain diagrams, and how are they distributed by diagram type?

Table 5 presents the distribution of image categories across repositories. Approximately 10% of the repositories containing images included some diagram, corresponding to 3.7% of the total repositories analyzed. This suggests that embedding diagrams as images directly within repositories is not a common practice among developers.

Table 4

Distribution of images by category.

Category	Number	Proportion	Avg confidence
None	2,412,201	97.89%	0.9941
Activity Diagram	4567	0.19%	0.7994
Sequence Diagram	3287	0.13%	0.8512
Class Diagram	26,975	1.09%	0.8555
Component Diagram	8177	0.33%	0.8068
Use Case Diagram	4906	0.20%	0.8432
Cloud Diagram	4161	0.17%	0.7556
Any Diagram	52,073	2.11%	0.8335

Table 5

Distribution of images by repository.

Category	Repositories	Proportion
None	96,555	98.32%
Activity Diagram	1810	1.84%
Sequence Diagram	1355	1.38%
Class Diagram	5774	5.88%
Component Diagram	3351	3.41%
Use Case Diagram	1997	2.03%
Cloud Diagram	1757	1.79%
Any Diagram	10,642	10.84%
Total with Image	98,207	100%
Total	287,201	-

Table 6

Difference in days between the diagram’s last update and the repository’s last update.

Category	Days
None	351
Activity Diagram	513
Sequence Diagram	482
Class Diagram	561
Component Diagram	526
Use Case Diagram	666
Cloud Diagram	530
Any Diagram	554

6.4. RQ4 - How do the timestamps of the last diagram update compare with the repository’s latest commit, and what does this indicate about the relevance and utility of these diagrams?

Table 6 illustrates the time difference between the last commit that modified a diagram and the last commit of the repository. On average, images identified as diagrams were last updated 554 days before the latest repository commit. This significant time gap suggests that these diagrams may no longer accurately represent the current state of the source code, potentially reducing their relevance and utility in ongoing development processes.

The substantial lag between the last update of the diagrams and the latest code commits implies that while diagrams are included in the repositories, they are not frequently updated to reflect recent changes in the codebase. This lack of synchronization can diminish the diagrams’ usefulness for developers who rely on up-to-date visual representations to understand the software’s architecture and design. Furthermore, this observation supports the notion that diagrams, while present, may be treated as supplementary documentation rather than integral components of the software design process.

7. Discussion: Art, philosophy, and science of software design

As stated in the introduction and supported by the results discussed above, we expect the research presented here to open the road to the development of better tools to support quantitative analysis of software repositories while also motivating researchers to explore some of

the most challenging and interesting questions regarding computation, knowledge, and design. This section further discusses the implications of the empirical results and elaborates on possible scientific conjectures and research paths regarding software design.

7.1. What is software design?

Academia and practitioners have proposed various methods for software design, ranging from formal methods and semi-formal diagram specifications to treating code as the primary design artifact. These approaches have sparked significant debates and the emergence of differing schools of thought concerning the “best” technique for software design. Traditionally, these discussions have been philosophical and qualitative. However, with the advent of repository mining techniques and machine learning algorithms, we can now provide quantitative evidence to support or challenge these theories.

Let us argue that source code is the only software documentation that seems to satisfy the criteria of an engineering design, as first proposed by Jack W. Reeves in [7]. Concretely, he states that any engineering task aims to produce some kind of documentation. Such documentation is called a design if it can be handed to a manufacturing team to produce and reproduce the desired product several times. Thus, according to his theory, the source code is the only documentation that satisfies the criteria during software development. Other design artifacts, such as design diagrams or formal models, are just auxiliary to the production of the actual design.

If the hypothesis is true, we may expect the auxiliary artifacts to be present in very few quantities and produced only to support the creation of the actual design. In our experiments, we found precisely that. We observed a low presence of diagrams in code repositories, with only 3.7% of them including software diagrams (see RQ2 and RQ3). Most of these diagrams were class diagrams, accounting for 51.8%, followed by component diagrams, which represent 15.7% of the total (see RQ3). Additionally, these diagrams often become outdated, with an average gap of 554 days between the last repository update and the most recent diagram (see RQ4).

Some may argue that the experiment is inconclusive concerning the suitability of design diagrams as valid media of design recording and that other design artifacts may be stored in private storage or separated from the source code. We must admit that this may be true, but it seems implausible that we will find different results by mining all possible digital storage related to software projects. It is also clear that a difference in the time stamps of source code and design diagrams may not indicate that the diagram is outdated. Although we expect this to be true, future research comparing the semantic content of such diagrams with source code using methods similar to those proposed here may explicitly verify such a hypothesis. Moreover, it is likely that formal methods advocates and design diagram proponents will continue to view these techniques as essential components of software design rather than merely auxiliary methods, as Reeves suggests. While our findings support the centrality of source code, differing perspectives on the role of formal methods and diagrams remain an integral part of the ongoing discourse in software engineering.

7.2. Toward a new theory of software design

So how can we solve the question of “how to design software”? It may seem that gathering evidence does not improve the discussion, and we are back to qualitative and philosophical arguments. However, we disagree.

No amount of evidence will indeed prove that a hypothesis is true. We do not state that empirical evidence proves a theory. We argue that the tools proposed here improve our capacity to generate evidence that may support or criticize our theories. Apart from evidence, we must develop a theory and a good explanation of software design.

But, again, how can we develop such a theory? Research and discussion on what constitutes software design have been put aside in the community. During the last few years, the software research community has retreated into behaviorism and empiricism, concentrating on analyzing outputs and improving tools.

We think the emergence of repository mining techniques supported by machine learning algorithms trained with large datasets constitute ideal tools to address difficult questions regarding the art, philosophy, and science of software engineering. Here, we investigated techniques to gather and analyze data using repository mining and ML techniques (see RQ1) to study software engineering hypotheses. But we want to motivate the missing part of the equation, the research on a theory of design. The results presented here are part of a broader research effort that is looking to address explicitly the problem of the nature of software design. We think that new developments in epistemology and the foundation of computing as a branch of physics may provide new insights into this matter.

A promising road of theoretical research could be found in K. Popper’s theory of knowledge [39,40] and the concept of abstract constructors proposed by D. Deutsch [41]. First, Popper proposes a theory of knowledge as conjectured explanations, where evidence is not a way of validating theories but only a way of testing them. Design is knowledge creation and is then a conjectured explanation. But what about documenting such knowledge? Here, D. Deutsch proposes Constructor Theory, which seeks to express all fundamental scientific theories in a dichotomy between possible and impossible physical transformations. The theory has several good properties, including that, contrary to other theories of physics, it allows exact statements of some emergent laws of physics, such as the second law of thermodynamics [42]. It also allows formulations of other emergent phenomena, such as knowledge, information [43], and intelligence. In such a theory, we found the concepts of Constructor and Abstract Constructor. A constructor is anything that can cause a transformation in physical systems without undergoing any net change in its ability to do so. An abstract constructor is, for example, a computer program.

Getting back to the original discussion on “What is Software design?”, let us call the *prevailing theory of software design*, or *Paper Software Design (PSD)*, the set of all theories advocating for software design to be recorded in paper (or any other static representation) instead of the source code, and let us call the *New Theory of Software Design* a theory advocating for design as a knowledge creation activity where source code is the only software documentation that satisfies the criteria of an engineering design.

We think constructor theory can provide some elements to compare paper software design (PSD) with the New Theory, giving an objective comparison criteria. A criterion could be, for example, *what kind of design documentation is better as an input for an abstract constructor*. With this criterion, we can create arguments as the following: PSD suffers from at least two problems: (1) Design gets outdated, then it loses its ability to reproduce the computer program that it is supposed to represent; (2) PSD needs the interpretation of a human constructor to reproduce it, and most probably the interpretation of that human constructor will not be the same computer program each time, even if the same constructor follows the same design. On the other hand, source code can be reproduced perfectly by an abstract constructor: the compiler program. In the new theory, designs do not get outdated because they represent precisely the program they are supposed to represent, and the compiler always produces the product that the designs represent.

What about artificial intelligence and Large Language Models (LLMs)? Do they constitute abstract constructors that consume design diagrams to produce software? We think current artificial intelligence programs, such as LLMs, could constitute abstract constructors that may always reproduce the same program if we program them to do so. For example, we can state that if the specification is complete enough, the LLM should compile the program instead of generating the

code. However, to the best of our knowledge, no diagram language provides enough expressive power to fully specify a program without some additional codification. The LLMs may, however, hallucinate and produce programs from incomplete diagrams. In that case, it will imitate a human constructor, although it will not generate any new knowledge. Conversely, Artificial General Intelligence (AGI), once achieved, will act as a creative constructor and programmer capable of developing diverse programs from the same set of complete or incomplete design diagrams. In this scenario, the AGI will not merely imitate human behavior; it will be a person who will consume design diagrams and source code as we do, using creativity and criticism.

A deeper discussion of Constructor Theory and its relation with knowledge, design, artificial intelligence, and the physical foundations of computation is outside the scope of this paper. But, again, we expect the research presented here to open the road to the development of better tools to support quantitative analysis of software repositories while also motivating researchers to explore some of the most difficult and interesting questions regarding computation, knowledge, and design.

8. Threats to validity

In this section, we discuss possible threats to validity. First, we discuss threats to validity during the construction and training of the classifier. We then discuss threats to validity during the repository mining phase and during the discussion and interpretation of the results.

Threats to validity during the training phase:

1. **Sampling Bias:** To mitigate sampling bias, the dataset was compiled by aggregating images from diverse sources. These included results obtained through web scraping using Google's image search engine, direct scraping of Git repositories, and a subset of approximately 600 images from the Lindholmen UML dataset [15]. The final dataset comprises 5981 images labeled using semi-automated techniques.
2. **Measurement Validity:** Although the dataset contains nearly 6000 images, it may be considered small relative to the millions of assets analyzed in the mining phase. To ensure the stability and reliability of the model's performance, we employed a Monte Carlo cross-validation. Specifically, rather than static folds, we randomly partitioned the dataset into training (80%) and validation (20%) subsets. This process was repeated four times using distinct random seeds to ensure independence. We then calculated the mean Accuracy and F1-score across these iterations to report the final metrics.

Now we consider the threats to the validity while using the model to investigate Q2, Q3, and Q4 on software repositories:

1. **Researcher bias:** Researcher bias refers to the influence that a researcher's personal beliefs, values, or preferences may have on the design, execution, or interpretation of a study. To address researcher bias in our study, we provide a replication package to promote transparency and ensure the reproducibility of our findings (see [35–38]). The replication package includes the original data and the algorithms used in the study, allowing other researchers to verify and independently replicate our results.

Dataset Relevance: Our training dataset was constructed from three complementary sources: Google Image Search, the Lindholmen UML dataset, and real assets extracted from Git repositories. This hybrid approach is relevant to the study because each source contributes a distinct form of visual variability that is necessary for training a robust classifier. Google Image Search provides clean, canonical examples of UML and architecture diagrams, allowing the model to learn the core structural patterns of each diagram type. The Lindholmen dataset adds

curated, research-grade UML models with consistent notation, strengthening the classifier's ability to generalize across standard representations. Finally, images extracted from Git repositories introduce realistic noise, stylistic diversity, and non-diagram artifacts that reflect the conditions encountered during large-scale mining. Together, these sources provide a balanced, representative set of examples that enable the classifier to perform reliably on heterogeneous images from real-world repositories.

2. **Construct Validity:** While designing the research questions, we concentrated on quantitative measurements of repository assets and avoided qualitative inferences. For example, instead of asking, "What artifacts do practitioners use to document design?" we preferred to investigate, "How common is it to upload images to GitHub repositories, and if they are diagrams, what kind of diagrams are they?" (see Q2). Thus, we try to use the model to answer concrete quantitative questions regarding the usage of design diagrams and let the qualitative interpretation to the section where we analyze the results. Additionally, while we employed a rigorous consensus process to resolve labeling discrepancies, we did not calculate a formal statistical metric for inter-rater reliability (such as Cohen's Kappa) prior to the consensus phase. This limits our ability to mathematically quantify the inherent ambiguity of specific diagram classes.
3. **External Validity:** External validity refers to generalizing study findings to real-world settings. Our study was conducted on randomly selected repositories in Github, and it may be considered a controlled environment, which may limit the generalizability of the results to other software development settings. Although we think Github's repositories reflect the current state of development techniques and methodologies, future research could include diverse developer populations and examine the phenomenon in non-public repositories and on-premises DevOps infrastructure to enhance external validity. The discussion and interpretation of the results link conjectures and hypotheses to the experimental findings. While we recognize that others may criticize such links, our purpose is to explore new paths of theoretical research on the nature of software design and show that repository mining may provide experimental outcomes to support or discard such conjectures.
4. **Internal Validity:** Numerical instability during training was mitigated by using the Adam optimizer with adaptive learning rates and early stopping. To control for random initialization effects, we reported results across multiple training iterations with different random seeds. Additionally, the "freshness" metric relies on Git timestamps, however, a diagram file might be "touched" in a commit without meaningful semantic updates, which is a known limitation in mining software repositories. Finally, regarding dataset partitioning, we employed random shuffling rather than a repository-aware split. While this ensures a statistical distribution of classes, it is possible that diagrams from the same repository (sharing visual styles) appear in both the training and validation sets. We mitigated this risk by ensuring a diverse set of repositories during initial scraping, but we acknowledge this as a limitation common to large-scale image mining.
5. **Reliability:** While designing the experiments and creating the dataset, we avoided inferential questions and used randomly selected samples to avoid bias and overfitting. While using the already-trained model during the experiments, we randomly chose repositories to prevent biased interpretation. The training dataset, with 5981 images, and the investigation of 2,469,206 repositories may be considered small compared with the more than 330 million repositories on GitHub. The training dataset may be enriched with additional diagram categories to improve results, and the experiment may also be applied to all available public repositories. The results discussed were performed over a

Fig. A.1. Graphic representation of the first six (6) feature maps for each layer belonging to a convolutional neural network trained to classify cats and dogs. The maps were generated from an image of a dog.

Fig. A.2. Representation of a pattern of spatial hierarchy of visual modules: hyper-local edges combine into local objects such as eyes or ears, which combine into high-level concepts such as “dog”.

small set of repositories. However, we expect them to represent current software practitioners’ behavior. However, the results may vary in the future as the knowledge and techniques of software design and construction evolve, for example, with the massification of Generative Artificial Intelligence in the software industry.

No investigation is immune to threats to validity. We expect this section to promote transparency and encourage further research that builds on, refines, and critiques our findings.

9. Conclusions and future work

In this study, we build a dataset [37] of 5981 labeled images extracted from GitHub repositories. We label those images according to the type of design diagram represented: activity, sequence, class, component, use case, and cloud diagrams. We then used a general-purpose dataset (ImageNet) to train a convolutional neural network classifier. Then, using transfer learning and the design diagrams dataset, we

further specialize the classifier to recognize images of software design diagrams. The trained model achieved an accuracy of 98.6% (0.986 ± 0.0017) and an F1-score of 98.3% (0.983 ± 0.0025) on the validation subset. Finally, we applied repository mining techniques to over half a million GitHub repositories, revealing insights into how software engineers use diagrams in their projects. Our analysis found that diagrams are not commonly used in repositories, with only 3.7% of code repositories containing software diagrams. Furthermore, the diagrams are prone to becoming outdated, with an average difference of 554 days between the last repository update and the image. The two most common diagram types are class diagrams, which account for 51.8% of the total, and component diagrams, which account for 15.7%. These results may already be used to understand which kinds of artifacts practitioners use for design. In particular, they indicate that source code may be the primary source of design information. Of course, these results are preliminary, and further investigation is needed. In particular, future research should investigate the semantic interpretation of diagrams and the use of mining techniques to extract design information from source code. For example, how to extract semantic information from code representations in [44]. In the paper, we also explore conjectures on possible empirical and theoretical links between knowledge, computation, design, and physics, primarily focused on Constructor Theory. Apart from exploring such conjectures, we want to motivate researchers to address deep questions about knowledge and design that we believe the software community has set aside.

Our research demonstrates the utility of repository mining techniques for studying software engineering practices and provides insights into how practitioners use software diagrams in repositories. The proposed classifier can also help identify diagram-type documentation artifacts, thereby facilitating future repository mining research. For instance, it could be applied to the problem of Traceability Link Recovery (TLR) to automate the recovery of links between code artifacts, documentation, and tests [45]. While new research in this field, such as [46], incorporates machine learning strategies to automate natural language processing (NLP), these techniques have not yet been applied to software diagrams in images.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sergio Rodríguez: Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Daniel Benavides:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Héctor Cadavid:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Wilmer Garzón:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used Grammarly and ChatGPT to improve readability and language and to check grammar. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix. Conceptual illustrations of CNNs and transfer learning

See Figs. A.1–A.3.

Fig. A.3. Diagram illustrating how transfer learning is applied to a pre-trained CNN for detecting handwritten letters of the alphabet to train a new network for detecting handwritten digits.

Data availability

The labeled images, the complete dataset, and the trained model are publicly available, and the corresponding references are provided in the manuscript.

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